

K-Means Clustering Resolution of Diurnal Wind Pattern Modes and Pattern Extrema for Nashville, TN (1948-2024)

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- ABSTRACT

Applying K-Means Clustering Analysis on contiguous hourly 0000 LST to 2300 LST wind direction/speed data for Nashville, TN. (1948-2024), the following identifies the station's most prominent diurnal statistical sub-patterns or "modes". The daily observations are first converted into 24 pairs of north/south and east/west components, and saved in an array of N by 48 cases, where N is the number of complete daily hourly observations and 48 the (standardized) magnitudes of the "u" and "v" parameter values. The K-Means clustering routine is then run, integrated with the V-Fold Cross Validation algorithm which produces an "optimal" number of "K" clusters. Each of the 48-D centroids (five in number) are then transformed into arrays of hourly resultant wind directions and mean scalar speeds. The results exhibit physically meaningful, distinct diurnal patterns, with contrasting seasonal inclinations as well. Then, as a heuristic exercise, the extreme-most diurnal wind pattern is identified, based on squared Euclidean distances generated by a fixed K=1 (global) treatment of the data. A recent similar analysis such as this one yielded good results for Las Vegas, Phoenix, and Tucson (Fisk, 2025).

- INTRODUCTION

Climatological wind variability is an important consideration in the planning of outdoor activities in which directions and speeds are expected to be of potential impact. Tabular summaries or graphical decision aid charts such as wind rose diagrams, products which denote or depict relative observed frequencies and mean speeds at various compass directions, can provide useful information for hours of interest, either individual or in combined, composited form..

If a graphical version of a given month's fine-scale *diurnal* contiguous wind character is of particular interest, a range of individual hours' wind roses would be suitable because wind variability during the day is influenced by such factors as solar insolation, or (in the case of coastal stations) sea-breeze and land-breeze preferred transition periods, not to mention in overall cases, seasonally preferred synoptic-scale influences such as cold spells, warm spells, or frontal approaches or passages. If an every-hour treatment is desired, that would require 24 sets of wind roses, requiring a large collection of raw observations, data reductions and analyses, and then, if desired, graphical transformations into wind rose charts.

If the preference is enlarged to a *global* fine-scale analysis involving data for every month and hour of the day, (a 288-numbered wind rose problem) this would be a laborious task, one that could influence backstepping to a lesser fraction of hours per month, say, every-third hour (or alternatively three-hour moving averages at three hour forward steps). In past years this latter method of choice was actually utilized by the NOAA National Climatic Data Center, now NCEI (National Centers for Environmental Information). but large volumes of output were still the result. This high-volume factor is probably why most wind roses diagrams/tabular summaries are not all-inclusive as to hour-of-the day.

An ultimate goal would thus be a methodology that is both fine scaled and global, depicting climatological wind variability information for each individual hour, by month, but most importantly, producing a small volume of output, while still permitting quick-study interpretations.

- METHODOLOGY AND DATA

- Diurnal Wind Pattern Modes

To this end, a technique has been developed that utilizes K-Means Clustering analyses of a given station's hourly wind history, facilitating creation of an abbreviated set of climatologically prominent individual-hour diurnal statistical wind patterns or "modes". A number of stations in southwestern California (nine) and Nevada/Arizona (three) have already been investigated in this manner with good results, and the present research applies the methodology on Nashville winds, covering its 1948-2024 period of record, including 19764 days' complete hourly observations, comprising 75% of the total 26297 daily observations. It's assumed that the Nashville wind climatology has not experienced any significant long-term trends in character since 1948.

The K-Means analysis for Nashville produces five diurnal statistical modes, the outputs summarized in single 24-row tables. Eight columns are displayed per table (See Figures 3 thru 8 below): from left-to-right: Hour of the day (LST), Resultant Wind Direction (both text and symbolic vector representations), Mean Scalar Wind Speed (knots), Vector Wind Constancy (both text and color-coded symbols - see Figure 9 below for the Constancy Color-coding Key chart), and Percent Occurrence Frequencies of the mode across half-month calendar segments. The half-month interval option, advantageously, effectively doubles the climatological resolution; conceivably, given the large sample size of the data set, the resolution could be increased to every-third month (~ 10 days), with no serious sample size issues (effectively nearly 900 wind roses or tabular summaries). Included also is a single summary time-series plot that depicts the five modes' half-month percent occurrence frequencies across the segments (See Figure 7). Thus, the Nashville modal results comprise just six charts (not including a chart of the data analyzed as an all-inclusive un-clustered entity), allowing for relatively speedy inspections and general insights concerning Nashville diurnal wind pattern contrasts over the calendar year. Since the five diurnal modes are fixed in hourly patterns by the clustering operation, aside from some basic comparative descriptions of their properties, the bulk of the more detailed characterizations are done in terms of the modes' contrasting seasonal attributes (i.e., percent frequency contrasts half-month to half-month segment).

The K-Means routine utilizes a special add-on tool, the V-fold Cross-Validation optimization algorithm (Burman, 1989) which determines an "optimal" number of clusters. The tool is an automated, iterative, training sample/testing sample procedure that rapidly produces in ascending order, K different cluster sets, the iterations ceasing at some "optimal" number K. Each iteration produces a slightly improved mean error ("cluster cost") of the observations relative to its revised K+1 centroid, and if the given iteration's cluster cost is less than five percent better, the iterations cease and the K results are selected as the "optimal" or "best" cluster set. In reality, this five percent improvement threshold is just a software default, and it's possible to lower the threshold (resulting in more clusters), or fix the number at K clusters. In this investigation the Squared Euclidean distance metric is selected, the other alternatives being Euclidean, City Block, and Chebychev.

- Pattern Extrema

Also, as an additional "spin-off" exercise, the extreme-most individual Nashville diurnal wind pattern is identified. To explain, among the diagnostics' outputs from the K-Means analyses, Squared Euclidean distance magnitudes for each of the original observations relative to their kth-cluster centroids are generated. However, the notion of "global" statistical distances, those produced if the observations are not clustered (i.e., a "forced" k=1 treatment, of which the software can perform, can be useful). An absolute maximum 48-D, K=1 distance could be interpreted heuristically as representing the most extreme individual hour-to-hour standardized "u" and "v" daily wind pattern. The more formal alternative would be the seemingly intractable task of fashioning a theoretical, parameter-based application for 48-D data. So, adopting the K=1

“workaround”, utilizing Squared Euclidean distances rather than parameter values, the single-most extreme diurnal wind pattern can be identified. Such extreme statistical distances are functions of anomalously high standardized u and v magnitudes (i.e., reflecting high wind speeds), unusually placed standardized u and v combinations (i.e., reflecting wind direction anomalies), and uncommon combinations of both wind speeds and directions at atypical hours of the day.

As described above, multiple distance metrics are available; however, the squared Euclidean is chosen over the Euclidean, as the latter applies the square root function, which compresses distances. The former retains the distances in original form which is advantageous to interpretations, as the extremes remain more visible and “fleshed out”. Two others are available, the City-Block and Chebychev, the City Block more applicable on integer data, the more complex Chebychev considered less applicable to wind-component data. Mean overall observational distance error for the K=1 operation was 0.591, (about double that of K=5’s 0.298).

- **RESULTS** -

- **Scree Plot and Summary Half-Month Frequency Climatological Time-Series Plot of the Modes**

Figure 1 below is a Scree Plot of the Nashville K-Means Cluster Analysis. As described in the previous section, determination of the “optimal” cluster number K was an iterative process in which successive K and K+1 cluster costs were compared in sequence as to their percent improvement deltas. In this Nashville analysis the K=6 cost (0.285) was less than 5% reduced (-4.13%) than K=5’s (0.298), so the iterations ceased, and k=5 was deemed as the “best cluster”.

FIGURE 1
Scree Plot for K-Means Cluster Analysis Resolution
of Nashville, TN Diurnal Wind Pattern Modes
(1948-2024 Hourly Data)

Next, Figure 2 below is a summary time-series graph depicting the modes' individual half-month to half-month frequency percentages, providing information on their seasonal proclivities. Reflecting Nashville's continental location in the heart of the mid-latitude westerlies' region of North America, the five patterns, with one exception, exhibit essentially unidirectional resultant wind directions, hour-to-hour, the main orientations being SSE'lys, Southerlies, NNE'lys, and NW'lys. The exception is one in which the hourly resultants are mostly SW'ly quadrant through early afternoon but diverge gradually in counter-clockwise fashion to WNW'lys by late in the evening.

FIGURE 2
Time-Series Plot of Nashville Diurnal Modes' Percent Frequencies at Half-Month Intervals

- Nashville Ranked Mode #1 – “Light SSE’ly’s to SE’lys Throughout (27.7% Frequency)

Ranking first in Nashville overall incidence is the “Light SSE’lys to SE’lys Throughout” Mode (See Figure 3 below), comprising 27.7% of the 19764 complete hourly cases. This reflects to a large extent the semi-permanent Azores-Bermuda High Pressure Area “Center of Action”, a major atmospheric feature that influences surface wind character in the southeastern United States, especially in summer. For Nashville, on a half-month to half-month percent frequency basis (see Figure 2) it’s the primary mode for the eleven contiguous segments MY2 (16-31 May) to OC2 (16-31 October), including an individual maximum 43.54 % percentage for AU2 (16-31 August). Explaining AU2’s percentage calculation: as some 820 1948-2024 cases were tallied between 16 and 31 August, and 357 were binned by K-Means into the “Light SSE’lys to SE’lys” cluster, the percent incidence was 357/820 multiplied 100 or the above 43.54% figure.

Column 2 in Figure 3 shows the mean resultant hourly 16-point compass directions (text) and Column 3 (symbolic vector equivalents); the hourly directions are either SE’ly, SSE’ly, or S’ly. Mean scalar wind speeds (column 4) in the aggregate are lightest of the five modes, ranging from

2.9 knots at 05 LST to 5.8 knots at 14 LST and 15 LST, the overall mean 4.4 knots. The vector wind constancy statistics (text in column 5 and color symbols in column 6) represent the persistency character of the resultant directions, the higher the statistic the more persistent the directions within the hourly data set in question. In the mean, Mode 1's constancy statistics are the lowest of the five modes (40.7), the hourly magnitudes typically in the mid 20's to the 40's, except the 60's for the day's closing three hours.

This suggests that while the mean resultant directions on balance are confined to a narrow net range of SE'lys to SSE'lys at light mean scalar speeds there may be a fair amount of variability towards other similar directions, also at light speeds, or even lighter speeds at SE'lys to SSE'lys orientations. The constancy color representations in Column 6 are based on a scale from 0 to 100 (See Appendix 1 below), the progression in rough terms: "red" (zero constancy), to "dark blue" (100 constancy). The latter 100 would be a case in which all the resultant directions for the given hour are of the same direction, a zero magnitude one in which the resultant directions' variabilities are such that they cancel each other out vectorially, indicative of very light, or directions of opposite character.

FIGURE 3
 Nashville Ranked Mode #1 – "Light SSE'lys TO SE'lys Throughout" - (27.7% Overall Frequency)

Nashville Ranked Mode #1 Pattern (27.7%)							
"Light SSE'lys to SE'lys Throughout" - MY2 to OC2 Prevalence							
HRLST	Resultant Wind Dir	Resultant Wind Dir	Mean Scalar Speed (kts)	Directional Constancy	Directional Constancy	Half Month Period	Percent Frequency
0	SSE		3.7	27.0	●	JA1	18.8
1	SSE		3.4	25.1	●	JA2	19.0
2	SSE		3.2	24.9	●	FB1	21.2
3	SSE		3.0	25.4	●	FB2	19.8
4	SE		3.0	28.9	●	MR1	16.4
5	SE		2.9	32.9	●	MR2	18.9
6	SE		3.0	37.0	●	AP1	16.6
7	SE		3.3	41.0	●	AP2	21.5
8	SE		3.8	43.1	●	MY1	26.6
9	SSE		4.6	43.6	●	MY2	31.6
10	SSE		5.0	41.9	●	JU1	33.1
11	SSE		5.4	38.7	●	JU2	32.5
12	SSE		5.6	36.5	●	JL1	36.5
13	SSE		5.7	34.0	●	JL2	41.0
14	SSE		5.8	35.5	●	AU1	38.6
15	SSE		5.8	35.8	●	AU2	43.5
16	SSE		5.7	38.8	●	SE1	39.7
17	SE		5.2	41.4	●	SE2	35.6
18	SE		4.8	45.8	●	OC1	37.0
19	SSE		4.5	52.2	●	OC2	31.9
20	SSE		4.5	58.4	●	NV1	26.2
21	SSE		4.5	62.9	●	NV2	23.5
22	SSE		4.5	63.5	●	DC1	23.1
23	S		4.4	63.3	●	DC2	23.4

- **Nashville Ranked Mode #2 – “Moderate Southerlies Throughout (22.7% Frequency)**

Ranking second in overall incidence is the “Moderate Southerlies Throughout” pattern (Figure 4 below) comprising 22.7% of the 1948-2024 cases. This seems to reflect the proximity of frontal zones, like the warm-sector of a low pressure system or alternatively, clockwise flow around the back side of ridge producing warming trends. From the Figure 2 summary plot, Mode #2 is the most prominent pattern for the contiguous six half-month periods FB2 (16-end February) to MY1 (1-15 May), and the four adjacent ones NV1 (1-15 November) to DC2 (16-31 December), and from Column 8, the two highest individual frequencies are seen for AP2 (33.7%) and AP1 (33.1%). The AU1 mid-summer figure, in contrast, is only 10.1%. From Column 2 the 16-point compass directions are all southerlies with the exceptions of SSE’ly for 04 LST and 05 LST and a SSE’ly for 13 LST. Mean diurnal scalar wind speeds (column 4) range from 6.1 knots to 11.5 knots, the aggregate average: 8.6 knots. The vector wind constancy statistics are all at “blue” or high levels, exceeding 90 magnitudes between 08 LST and 16 LST. Overall mean is 88.0.

FIGURE 4
Nashville Ranked Mode #2 – “Moderate Southerlies Throughout” - (22.7% Overall Frequency)

Nashville Ranked Mode #2 Pattern (22.7%)							
"Moderate Southerlies Throughout" -MR2 thru AP2 & DC2 Prevalence							
HRLST	Resultant Wind Dir	Resultant Wind Dir	Mean Scalar Speed (kts)	Directional Constancy	Directional Constancy	Half Month Period	Percent Frequency
0	S	↑	6.3	84.4	●	JA1	24.9
1	S	↑	6.2	85.1	●	JA2	24.3
2	S	↑	6.1	85.4	●	FB1	21.1
3	S	↑	6.2	85.7	●	FB2	24.8
4	SSE	↑	6.2	86.1	●	MR1	28.7
5	SSE	↑	6.3	87.3	●	MR2	29.6
6	S	↑	6.6	88.0	●	AP1	31.3
7	S	↑	7.2	89.2	●	AP2	33.7
8	S	↑	8.4	90.1	●	MY1	27.6
9	S	↑	9.7	91.2	●	MY2	23.3
10	S	↑	10.6	91.2	●	JU1	18.6
11	S	↑	11.2	91.4	●	JU2	17.2
12	S	↑	11.4	91.8	●	JL1	14.6
13	SSW	↑	11.5	91.6	●	JL2	12.4
14	S	↑	11.5	91.4	●	AU1	10.6
15	S	↑	11.2	91.3	●	AU2	11.7
16	S	↑	10.6	91.3	●	SE1	15.2
17	S	↑	9.6	89.9	●	SE2	16.1
18	S	↑	8.7	88.7	●	OC1	17.7
19	S	↑	8.2	87.9	●	OC2	21.5
20	S	↑	8.2	87.0	●	NV1	26.9
21	S	↑	8.3	85.7	●	NV2	27.4
22	S	↑	8.3	81.9	●	DC1	29.7
23	S	↑	8.3	78.9	●	DC2	25.3

- **Nashville Ranked Mode #3 – “North to NNE’lys Throughout” (20.2% Frequency)**

Ranking third in overall incidence is the “North to NNE’lys Throughout” Pattern (Figure 5 below), comprising 20.2% of the 1948-2024 cases overall. This appears, in its most salient feature, to be a secondary mode of late summer (relative to Mode 1), with an abbreviated period of elevated incidence for the four successive half-month periods AU1 (1-15 August) thru SE2 (16-30 September), varying from 26.1% frequency for the former to 28.4% for the latter, still, however, well short of the statistics for Mode 1. Possibly this reflects occasional, temporary displacements or weakenings of the Azores-Bermuda High, allowing for flow from the northeast to pass through the Nashville area. From Column 2 the 16-point compass resultant directions are all northerlies from 00 LST to 06 LST, followed by NNE’lys for the remaining 17 hours. Mean diurnal scalar wind speeds (column 4) range from 4.8 knots to 8.1 knots, the overall mean: 6.5 knots. Vector wind constancies range from the low 60’s to the high 80’s, the overall average 75.9.

FIGURE 5
Nashville Ranked Mode #3 – “North to NNE’lys Throughout” –
(20.2% Overall Frequency)

Nashville Ranked Mode #3 Pattern (20.2%)							
"N to NNE'lys Throughout" - Most Frequent, AU1 thru SE2							
HRLST	Resultant Wind Dir	Resultant Wind Dir	Mean Scalar Speed (kts)	Directional Constancy	Directional Constancy	Half Month Period	Percent Frequency
0	↘	N	5.8	67.6	●	JA1	20.5
1	↘	N	5.7	70.5	●	JA2	21.0
2	↘	N	5.7	73.0	●	FB1	22.9
3	↘	N	5.6	74.5	●	FB2	20.9
4	↘	N	5.6	76.5	●	MR1	20.9
5	↘	N	5.5	77.8	●	MR2	20.2
6	↘	N	5.6	79.1	●	AP1	17.7
7	↘	NNE	6.1	81.5	●	AP2	16.1
8	↘	NNE	6.8	83.1	●	MY1	17.4
9	↘	NNE	7.2	83.1	●	MY2	19.6
10	↘	NNE	7.4	82.9	●	JU1	17.2
11	↘	NNE	7.5	83.0	●	JU2	16.9
12	↘	NNE	7.7	82.9	●	JL1	16.4
13	↘	NNE	7.8	83.7	●	JL2	17.8
14	↘	NNE	8.0	85.1	●	AU1	26.1
15	↘	NNE	8.1	86.2	●	AU2	26.2
16	↘	NNE	7.9	87.1	●	SE1	27.9
17	↘	NNE	7.5	87.5	●	SE2	28.4
18	↘	NNE	6.8	86.3	●	OC1	22.7
19	↘	NNE	6.1	84.6	●	OC2	18.7
20	↘	NNE	5.7	79.9	●	NV1	19.2
21	↘	NNE	5.5	74.4	●	NV2	16.0
22	↘	NNE	5.1	67.3	●	DC1	17.6
23	↘	NNE	4.8	61.7	●	DC2	19.0

- **Nashville Ranked Mode #4 – “Clockwise Turning, SSW’lys to WNW’lys” - 16.1% Frequency**

Fourth in overall frequency is the “Clockwise Turning (SSW’lys to WNW’lys)” configuration (Figure 6 below). This is the only pattern which exhibits a progressive change in directions, early to late. It’s at least suggestive of a late in the day comparatively weak (cold) frontal passage. A noticeable feature in the Percent Frequency column shows that the highest figures, ranging from 20.3% to 27.1%, are exhibited for the five adjacent JU1 (1-15 July) through AU1 (1-15 August) sequences during the height of summer. As NW’ly flow is infrequent at Nashville in summer (See the Figure 7 table below), perhaps what (brief) cooling spells do occur at this warm season would result from predominant Westerly to WNW’ly flow.

Mean diurnal scalar wind speeds (column 4) vary from 6.5 knots to 10.1 knots, the overall mean: 7.5 knots. The late hours’ WNW’lys average 6.6 knots, with constancies dropping into the high 40’s, but the earlier day SSW’lys to W’lys, thru 16 LST, have individual hourly constancies averaging 79.4, indicative of relatively homogeneous directions, hour-by-hour, up to that point.

FIGURE 6
Nashville Ranked Mode #4 - “Clockwise Turning (SSW’lys to WNW’lys)” – 16.1% Overall Frequency

Nashville Ranked Mode #4 Pattern (16.1%)							
“Clockwise Turning (SSW’lys to WNW’lys) thru day” - Most Frequent JU1 thru JL2							
HRLST	Resultant Wind Dir	Resultant Wind Dir	Mean Scalar Speed (kts)	Directional Constancy	Directional Constancy	Half Month Period	Percent Frequency
0	SSW	↗	6.7	77.1	●	JA1	15.2
1	SSW	↗	6.7	78.5	●	JA2	15.3
2	SSW	↗	6.6	78.0	●	FB1	13.0
3	SSW	↗	6.5	78.0	●	FB2	16.5
4	SSW	↗	6.5	78.7	●	MR1	15.5
5	SSW	↗	6.5	79.9	●	MR2	13.2
6	SSW	↗	6.5	79.0	●	AP1	16.6
7	SSW	↗	7.0	79.0	●	AP2	14.4
8	SW	↗	7.8	78.0	●	MY1	15.9
9	SW	↗	8.7	79.2	●	MY2	18.1
10	WSW	↗	9.3	80.6	●	JU1	22.8
11	WSW	↗	9.8	81.8	●	JU2	27.1
12	WSW	↗	10.1	81.9	●	JL1	25.5
13	WSW	↗	10.1	81.9	●	JL2	22.7
14	W	→	10.1	80.8	●	AU1	20.3
15	W	→	10.0	79.8	●	AU2	13.8
16	W	→	9.6	78.0	●	SE1	10.2
17	W	→	8.9	74.6	●	SE2	10.7
18	W	→	7.9	70.0	●	OC1	11.6
19	WNW	↙	7.1	63.1	●	OC2	12.6
20	W	→	6.9	56.0	●	NV1	11.7
21	WNW	↙	6.8	49.9	●	NV2	15.2
22	WNW	↙	6.6	47.1	●	DC1	14.9
23	WNW	↙	6.5	45.7	●	DC2	16.9

- **Nashville Ranked Mode #5 – “WNW’lys to NNW’lys Throughout” - 13.4% Frequency**

Fifth and last ranked is the “WNW’lys to NNW’lys Throughout” mode (Figure 7 below), displaying an overall 13.4% percent frequency. Clearly a cold-season predominant pattern, for the twelve successive sequences AP2 (16-30 April) thru OC1 (1-15 October), it’s the least frequent of the five, the figures less than 5 percent for AU1 (1-15 August – 4.5%) and AU2 (16-31 August - 4.8%). Maximum frequencies are for the three successive mid-winter periods, JA1 (1-15 January) to FB1 (1-15 February), the latter with the highest individual statistic (21.7%). Mean diurnal scalar wind speeds (column 4) vary from 6.0 to 10.8 knots, the grand mean: 8.7 knots, a bit higher than Mode 2’s 8.6 figure. Mean constancy is 79.5.

FIGURE 7
Nashville Ranked Mode #5 – “WNW’lys to NNW’lys Throughout” – 13.4 % Overall Frequency

Nashville Ranked Mode #5 Pattern (13.4%)							
HRLST	WNW'lys to NNW'lys Throughout - Least Frequent JL2 thru AU2		Mean Scalar	Directional	Directional	Half Month	Percent
	Resultant Wind Dir	Resultant Wind Dir	Speed (kts)	Constancy	Constancy	Period	Frequency
0	WNW		8.1	60.3		JA1	20.5
1	WNW		8.0	63.6		JA2	20.4
2	WNW		8.0	67.7		FB1	21.7
3	WNW		7.9	71.4		FB2	17.9
4	WNW		8.0	75.3		MR1	18.4
5	WNW		8.0	78.0		MR2	18.1
6	NW		8.1	80.4		AP1	17.7
7	NW		8.5	83.5		AP2	14.3
8	NW		9.2	86.2		MY1	12.5
9	NW		9.8	88.0		MY2	7.4
10	NW		10.2	88.7		JU1	8.4
11	NW		10.4	90.0		JU2	6.3
12	NW		10.7	90.3		JL1	7.0
13	NW		10.7	90.4		JL2	6.1
14	NW		10.8	89.9		AU1	4.5
15	NW		10.7	90.1		AU2	4.8
16	NW		10.2	89.7		SE1	7.0
17	NW		9.4	87.8		SE2	9.3
18	NW		8.4	85.5		OC1	11.0
19	NNW		7.4	81.5		OC2	15.3
20	NNW		6.9	76.1		NV1	16.1
21	NW		6.6	69.8		NV2	18.0
22	NW		6.3	64.8		DC1	14.7
23	NW		6.0	60.0		DC2	15.5

- **Nashville Overall Diurnal Wind Pattern Statistics and Determination of the “Extrememost” K=1 Pattern**

Lastly, analyzing Nashville’s 1948-2024 data set as an un-clustered K=1 entity, Figure 8 below, shows Nashville’s overall composite diurnal configuration. With three exceptions, hourly resultants are all in the southwesterly quadrant, the exceptions being westerlies for the adjacent hours 16 LST to 18 LST. However, reflecting Nashville’s variable wind character, demonstrated on a collective basis from Figures 3 through 7, constancies are all low, magnitudes confined to between 7.0 for 19 LST and 26.3 for 12 LST (see column 5). Thus, in summary, Nashville resultant wind directions have a slight vectorial “bent” towards flow from the SW, but their high statistical variability is a more significant feature.

FIGURE 8
Nashville Overall Diurnal Wind Pattern Statistics and
“Extrememost” K=1 Pattern

Nashville (All modes combined) - (K=1)							
"Large Variability w/SSW'ly to WSW'ly Net Inclination"						Extrememost Pattern	
HRLST	Resultant Wind Dir	Resultant Wind Dir	Mean Scalar Speed (kts)	Directional Constancy	Directional Constancy	WDIR	WSPDKT
0	SSW		5.3	22.3	●	SSW	8
1	SSW		5.1	21.9	●	WNW	20
2	SW		5.0	20.0	●	WNW	26
3	SW		5.0	19.5	●	NW	26
4	SW		5.0	18.6	●	WNW	20
5	SSW		5.1	18.5	●	WNW	22
6	SSW		5.5	18.1	●	WNW	25
7	SSW		6.3	16.4	●	WNW	20
8	SW		7.1	16.9	●	WNW	19
9	SW		7.7	19.9	●	W	22
10	SW		8.1	22.9	●	WNW	21
11	WSW		8.3	25.3	●	WNW	23
12	WSW		8.3	26.3	●	WNW	30
13	WSW		8.4	26.0	●	WNW	24
14	WSW		8.5	23.8	●	W	30
15	WSW		8.4	21.1	●	WNW	30
16	W		8.1	17.4	●	WNW	30
17	W		7.4	13.1	●	W	20
18	W		6.7	8.9	●	W	18
19	WSW		6.1	7.0	●	WNW	15
20	SSW		5.9	11.0	●	WNW	17
21	SSW		5.8	16.1	●	WNW	17
22	SSW		5.6	19.8	●	WNW	11
23	SSW		5.5	21.8	●	WNW	13

Also, based on the squared Euclidean Distance statistics provided for each of the 19764 observations in the forced K=1 treatment, the individual case with the most extreme distance was identified as the most “extreme” diurnal pattern. From Columns 7 and 8 in Figure 8 above, this was the hour-to-hour winds’ progression of 7 April 1956, one with mostly West to NW’ly throughout the day, at speeds mostly in excess of 20 knots, occasionally at 30 knots. The extreme statistical distance (4.655) could be attributed to the generally strong speeds, the relatively uncommon direction (NW’ly quadrant), and the particularly strong speeds in the pre-dawn hours, uncharacteristic of the typical diurnal cycle. Figure 9 is a histogram of the entire set of 19764 statistical distances.

FIGURE 9
Histogram of Nashville Overall K=1 Diurnal Wind Pattern Statistical Distance Magnitudes (1948-2024 Data)

- SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

The foregoing demonstrated the use of K-Means Clustering Analysis as a methodology for producing a concise, quick-study interpretation of Nashville, Tennessee's diurnal and seasonal wind climatology. The finished results were presented on just seven tables, packed with various hour-by-hour parameter information, both text and graphics.

From Figures 3 through 7, five principal diurnal patterns or modes were identified, four of which exhibited essentially unipolar resultant wind directions, 00 LST to 23 LST, the fifth displaying a gradual clockwise turning of the resultants Midnight to 2300 LST.

From Figure 2, the modes displayed on a seasonal basis contrasting half-month to half-month seasonal inclinations, mostly evident in the warmer months, also showing on occasion particularly high or low relative frequency concentrations confined over just a few adjacent half-month segments.

Then, in a heuristic "extreme-value" analysis, inspecting statistical distances from the overall 1948-2024 data set, as transformed into a $K=1$ cloud, the single-most Nashville extreme 24-hour pattern of scalar wind speeds and directions was identified.

The realization of five "best" cluster sets was a satisfactory result, as the diurnal patterns of four of the five were essentially unidirectional in resultant direction hour-by-hour. Nonetheless, it should be reiterated that the software's terminologies of "optimal" and "best" should not be regarded as be-all and end-all descriptions. The five percent improvement threshold cutoff was only a default, the "standard" not likely based on any theoretical considerations. "Optimal" results for the twelve stations in Southern California, Nevada, and Arizona previously analyzed by the five percent method (see References below) ranged from three to five idealized diurnal patterns.

In an experiment for the Nashville data, forcing a *two* percent cutoff threshold resulted in 10 "optimal" clusters, associated with a 0.251 cost, 15.7% better than the $K=5$ results, but consequently, of course, with more complex features likely to interpret. The cost curve at these higher K levels through at least 10, was asymptotic downward, no "bottoming-out" or "elbow-shaped" features that could serve as a convenient cutoff " K ").

The application of the fixed diurnal modal scheme across the whole calendar year as a single entity was done assuming that there would be no serious issues concerning variables such as seasonal progressions of daylight hour lengths. Mean hours of daylight in Nashville vary from 9.7 hours for DC2 (December 16-31) to 14.6 hours for JU2 (June 16-30), and insolation hours vary significantly as well. To investigate this, average composite cluster costs by half-month segment were calculated and plotted against those of the mean half-month daylight hours, together with the mean average overall cost figure for the complete analysis (.298) - See Figure 10 below.

Results display an inverse linear relationship ($r=-0.465$), the highest half-month costs/mean errors covering the contiguous segments over the colder and lower sun periods FB2 thru AP1 and NV2 thru DC2, respectively, approaching 0.40 magnitudes for the former and around 0.35 for the latter. Conversely, the lowest costs are noted for the warmer and higher sun period five contiguous segments AU1 thru OC1, as low as .213 for SE1. Thus, it appears that the length of daylight variable is not a factor, the contrasts having been assimilated into the five modes' diurnal statistical configurations. The variation in the costs was probably due instead to the climatologically greater variances and increased likelihoods of extreme wind episodes during late-February to early April, and late November through December.

FIGURE 10
 Mean Half-Month Costs (Red) vs. Mean Half-Month Daylight Hours (Blue) – Nashville Diurnal Winds K-Means Analysis (1948-2024)

The K-Means methodology utilized in this manner, decomposing a given station’s hourly historical data set into its constituent climatological sub-patterns has proved useful with other types of environmental variables. A few additional investigations along these lines appear below in the References section: 1.) Wind Patterns with Height (Rawinsonde data) at a Southern California Test Range, 2.) Two-station Joint hourly wind patterns during Santa Ana Wind episodes in Southern California, 3.) Relative Anomaly Patterns in Annual Total Precipitation Across New England NCDC Climate Divisions, 4.) Identification of California, Oregon, and Washington Coastal Area Climate Divisions' Relative Anomaly Patterns in Total Seasonal Precipitation Relative to El Nino, Neutral, and La Nina Episodes, and 5.) Climatological Wind-Wave/Swell Patterns (Directions and Speeds) for a resident Buoy in the Southern California Bight Area.

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[Clustering binary data with K-Means \(should be avoided\)](#)

Mathematics Stack Exchange, "[Why is squared Euclidean distance used for measuring similarity? Why is it squared?](#)"

APPENDIX 1

Mean Vector Wind Constancy Color Key

CONSTANCY
COLOR KEY:

 = 100

 = 90

 = 80

 = 70

 = 60

 = 50

 = 40

 = 30

 = 20

 = 10

 = 0